

Cooperative FSO and mmWave System for Reliable 200G Wireless Transmission

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Abstract—The use of free-space optics (FSO) for ultra-high-speed communications has been recently standing out as a promising alternative for fiber/wireless-based scenarios. However, FSO communications still suffer from variations in the received optical power due to atmospheric turbulence and weather instability, which limits its use in reliability-driven applications. To explore the full potential of FSO and maintain communications reliability, hybrid FSO and radio-frequency systems can be employed to leverage the strengths of the two technologies. In this paper, we demonstrate a 3 m hybrid FSO and millimeter-wave system for 200G stable wireless transmission. Resorting to time-adaptive probabilistic constellation shaping and a cross-domain entropy loading scheme, we are able to compensate for up to 15% (30 Gbps) of data-rate reduction in the FSO link. Comparing with FSO-only transmission, we demonstrate a cumulative capacity gain of over 150 Gbps after 40 offline measurement iterations.

Index Terms—free-space optics, millimeter-wave, probabilistic constellation shaping, atmospheric turbulence.

I. INTRODUCTION

FREE-space optics (FSO) has recently been attracting interest for a wide variety of high-speed applications such as 5G fronthaul [1], inter- and intra-datacenter [2] and satellite communications [3]. Due to its high-bandwidth, license-free spectrum and ease-of-deployment, free-space-optics (FSO) is being considered for last-mile access in scenarios where the fiber deployment is difficult and the RF systems cannot comply with the bandwidth requirements.

Also driven by the bandwidth demand and advances in low-power digital signal processing (DSP), coherent communications are becoming the dominant technology in high-capacity optical links, transitioning gradually from the long-haul to the datacenter space. Together with coherent communications, FSO can provide a seamless link preserving the bandwidth of the coherent transceiver, since the optical signal is directly coupled to the fiber core using fiber collimators. However, the performance of these systems is known to be severely impacted by the atmospheric turbulence that results in time-dependent fluctuations of the received optical power [4]. To deal with this phenomenon, several time adaptive techniques

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have been studied, such as transmitter power control [5], adaptive modulation [6] and coding [7]. More recently, probabilistic constellation shaping (PCS) has been introduced in coherent communications providing signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) gains in additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channels and allowing for enhanced flexibility and granular control of the bitrate [8]. The use of time-adaptive PCS for FSO links has recently been proposed, providing significant capacity gains in time-dependent power fading conditions [9]. Despite these overall advances for compensating the atmospheric turbulence (AT) in FSO links, feasible and reliable implementations need to rely on complementary solutions to provide some backup capacity. To that purpose, the use of hybrid radio-FSO transmission is a potential candidate for the design of reliable and high-capacity wireless links [10], with particular relevance for satellite-to-earth communication scenarios, where current millimeter-wave (mmWave) systems [11] and next-generation coherent FSO transmission [2] might provide a symbiotic approach.

In this work we experimentally demonstrate a 3 m cooperative FSO and mmWave link, with 200 Gbps stable transmission, using time-adaptive PCS and cross-domain entropy loading to dynamically balance the bitrate between the FSO and mmWave links, thereby improving the communication reliability and/or the average achievable data-rate.

II. CROSS-DOMAIN ENTROPY LOADING

A. PCS-based Bitrate Adaptation

Probabilistic constellation shaping has been widely shown as a promising technique to enhance system capacity by minimizing the transmitted signal energy. In AWGN channels, the minimum transmitted signal energy for a given bitrate is achieved by setting the quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) symbol probabilities according to the Maxwell-Boltzman distribution [12],

$$P_{x_n} = \frac{\exp(-\lambda|x_n|)^2}{\sum_{n=1}^M \exp(-\lambda|x_n|)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ is the shaping parameter and x_n is the n -th symbol in the square M -QAM constellation alphabet.

Besides enabling to reduce the average signal energy, PCS can also be used to adapt the transmitted signal entropy [12], $H_{\text{PCS}} = -\sum_{n=1}^M P_{x_n} \log_2(P_{x_n})$, and therefore the net bitrate by changing the shaping parameter, λ . Considering a system with PCS modulation and forward error correction (FEC), the relation between the system bitrate and the constellation entropy is given by,

$$R_b = N_{\text{pol}} R_S [H_{\text{PCS}} - (1 - R_{\text{FEC}}) \log_2 M] \quad (2)$$

TABLE I: Signal parameters used for the FSO and mmWave links.

Parameter	FSO	mmWave
R_S	40 Gbaud	5 Gbaud
N_{pol}	2	1
M	16	256
R_{FEC}	5/6	5/6

Fig. 1: Symbol probability distributions and signal entropy for different bitrates considering a 16QAM and 256QAM PCS constellations for the FSO (blue) and the mmWave (red) signals.

where R_b is the net bitrate, N_{pol} is the number of polarizations, R_S the operating symbol rate, R_{FEC} is the FEC rate and M is the QAM template for PCS. In order to correctly set the PCS shaping factor that maximizes the channel capacity, we need to evaluate beforehand the achievable information rate (AIR) for a given SNR. To that end, the normalized generalized mutual information (NGMI) is commonly utilized as a pre-FEC figure-of-merit in systems using soft-decision FEC [13]. It can be shown that the minimum NGMI required to ensure error-free transmission is equal to the FEC rate. However, due to the non-ideal FEC performance, one has to consider a slightly higher NGMI threshold, NGMI_{th} , than the minimum necessary. Note that for this work, we resort to the constant composition distribution matcher (CCDM) algorithm to implement the distribution matcher and dematcher.

To illustrate the PCS application in this work, let us consider the system specifications shown in Table I, that match the ones used in the experimental setup presented in section III. Utilizing expression (2) with the signal parameters shown in Table I, it results that the achievable net bitrates with the PCS scheme are within the interval of 106.6 Gbps to 266.6 Gbps and 8.3 Gbps to 33.3 Gbps for the FSO and mmWave links, respectively. These numbers show the larger bitrate adaptability in the FSO system due to its capability of operating at a significantly higher symbol rate. Since we target a stable 200 G, we set the FSO link to operate at a maximum net bitrate of 190 Gbps and the mmWave link to a minimum of 10 Gbps. Considering the bitrate selection range for the mmWave, we can expect the mmWave link to absorb up to 10% of bitrate loss in the FSO link *i.e.* the FSO bitrate could decrease down to 170 Gbps due to the impact of AT. Figure 1 shows the symbol probability distributions of the PCS constellations corresponding to bitrates in the range of 170–190 Gbps for the FSO and 10–30 Gbps for the mmWave.

In order to control the transmitted net bitrate, one must

 Fig. 2: Net bitrate adaptation by tuning the shaping parameter, λ , for the (a) FSO and (b) mmWave signals. Received constellations and SNR_{req} are shown for different bitrates considering a $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 0.88$.

adjust the shaping parameter, λ , accordingly to equation 1. Considering the aforementioned signal parameters, the dependence of λ on the transmitted net bitrate for both the FSO and mmWave links is shown in Fig 2. As expected in the FSO signal, a small variation (less than 0.05) of the λ parameter is sufficient to vary the bitrate from 170 Gbps to 190 Gbps. This also translates into a small difference in the required SNRs for the maximum and minimum net bitrates, approximately 0.88 dB. More importantly, it defines the maximum SNR penalty imposed by AT that can be supported. As opposed to the FSO signal, the mmWave one requires a higher variation of λ to adjust the bitrate since it operates at a lower symbol rate. As the mmWave link will not be subjected to any signal impairment, we only need to guarantee the required SNR to operate at 30 Gbps so in the worst-case scenario it can absorb the bitrate loss of the FSO. Along with the aforementioned SNR requirements, the maximum transmitted power is also important in the design of hybrid FSO-mmWave link, since both limit the link distance. In the case of the FSO, the transmitted optical power is defined by the optical amplifier that follows the optical modulator. The mmWave reach will mainly depend on the output power of the power amplifier and the directivity of the antennas used in the RF frontend.

B. Cross-Domain Entropy Loading Scheme

The proposed cross-domain entropy loading concept is presented in Fig. 3. The purpose of this system is to provide a mmWave channel parallel to the FSO capable of absorbing the capacity loss when the AT is present so that the overall data-rate is maintained. In this work, we consider a total net bitrate of 200 Gbps, which, in perfect channel conditions, is divided into 190 Gbps for the FSO and 10 Gbps for the mmWave link. The AT is introduced by an optical *fade emulator* [3], imposing a time-variant attenuation to the FSO signal before reaching the receiver. To estimate the impact of AT on the

Fig. 3: Proposed cross-domain entropy loading concept for a hybrid FSO-mmWave system impaired by atmospheric turbulence.

Fig. 4: a) Experimental setup of the cooperative FSO-mmWave link (inset in the middle of the figure). b) Attenuation used in the VOA to emulate the AT. c) Probability density function of the generated attenuation. d) Measured SNR of the FSO link as a function of the VOA attenuation.

link performance, we start by evaluating the NGMI of the received signal and its respective SNR for the current iteration. By assuming that the current and future attenuations to be imposed in the FSO link are known, *i.e.* assuming an ideal channel estimator, we can calculate the SNR of the received signal in the next iteration as,

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{est}}(k+1) = \text{SNR}_{\text{meas}}(k) - (\alpha(k+1) - \alpha(k)) \quad (3)$$

where SNR_{est} is the predicted SNR, SNR_{meas} is the SNR obtained from the measured NGMI and α is the attenuation imposed in the FSO link. Note that both attenuation and SNR are assumed to be measured in dB. Other alternatives could be used to estimate the channel SNR like a low-complexity moving average presented in [9].

With the estimated SNR, we can calculate a new achievable FSO net bitrate for a given NGMI threshold,

$$R_b(k+1) = 2R_s \text{AIR}(k+1) \quad (4)$$

where $R_b(k+1)$ is the achievable FSO net bitrate in the next iteration, R_s is the signal symbol rate and AIR is the theoretical estimation of the achievable information rate, which depends on the estimated SNR and NGMI threshold. The difference between the total net bitrate, 200 Gbps and the achievable FSO bitrate in the next iteration is the bitrate required for the mmWave link. Finally, the entropy of both the FSO and mmWave signals is adapted accordingly to the new bitrates.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup used in this work is depicted in Fig. 4a). The FSO signal is generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) with an analog bandwidth of 45 GHz operating at 120 GSa/s. The signal is designed with a 16 QAM-PCS template, a 20% overhead FEC and a symbol rate of 40 Gbaud. The optical modulation is performed by a dual-polarization IQ modulator, which is fed by a 1556 nm external cavity laser (ECL) with an output power of 15 dBm. The optical signal is then amplified by a 15 dB gain and 5 dB noise figure erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) to compensate for the IQ modulator losses. For the mmWave link, the digital signal is generated with a 256 QAM-PCS template, 20% FEC overhead and 5 Gbaud. The baseband signal is digitally upconverted to an intermediate-frequency (IF) carrier at 2.6 GHz and sent to an AWG with 8 GHz of analog bandwidth and operating at 16 GSa/s. The output of the AWG is amplified by a driver amplifier with 20 dB gain and 5 dB of noise figure before

driving an 18 GHz directly modulated laser (DML) operating at 1546 nm. Both the FSO and the mmWave optical signals are then combined using an add-drop multiplexer and sent through 8.2 km standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) before being demultiplexed again. The FSO optical signal is collimated in free-space using a commercial collimator with 24 mm of lens diameter, 0.24 numerical aperture and a divergence angle of 0.0017°. The receiver collimator is placed 3 m apart from the transmitter and features the same characteristics. A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is applied as a *fade emulator* [3], mimicking the AT effect by controlling the optical power that reaches the coherent receiver. The coherent receiver has 40 GHz of bandwidth and converts the optical signal to the electrical domain. The optical local oscillator is also an ECL with the same parameters as the one in the transmitter. The I and Q components of each polarization are collected from the coherent receiver by a 4-port real-time oscilloscope (RTO) with 70 GHz bandwidth and operating at 200 GSa/s. The optical signal corresponding to the mmWave link is fed to a positive-intrinsic-negative (PIN) diode with an integrated transimpedance amplifier (TIA). The mmWave upconverter takes the IF signal from the PIN and performs the mixing with a 24.8 GHz local oscillator, side-band filtering and low-noise amplification. It outputs a mmWave signal centered at 27.4 GHz that is amplified by a 20 dB gain power amplifier before being transmitted with a Ka-band horn antenna with 10 dBi gain. The receiver horn antenna is also located 3 m apart from the transmitter. It collects the mmWave signal that is amplified by a low-noise amplifier with 20 dB gain and 1.5 dB noise figure and then downconverted. The downconverter has the same architecture as the upconverter but performs the mixing, filtering and amplification in the reverse order. Finally, an RTO with 8 GHz bandwidth and 20 GSa/s samples the IF signal from the downconverter. The acquired signals from the RTOs are processed offline and subjected to standard DSP. For the FSO link, the DSP subsystems are: IQ imbalance compensation, 2×2 constant modulus algorithm (CMA)-based adaptive equalization (101 taps), frequency and phase recovery and least mean squares (LMS)-based equalization (101 taps). Regarding the mmWave link, the DSP applied is as follows: downconversion to baseband and a dual-stage LMS-based equalization with 51 taps in each stage.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The Gamma-Gamma (GG) model has been widely used to describe turbulence from the weak to the strong regime

Fig. 5: Evolution of a) NGMI and b) net bitrates for each iteration. The received constellations in iteration 28 are also shown in the insets.

[14]. However, the use of GG in this setup, even in the weak regime would impose large signal attenuation in the FSO channel which would require bitrate in the mmWave link that the hardware could not support. Since the probability density function (PDF) of the attenuation imposed by AT presents a quasi-Gaussian distribution for weak turbulence ($\sigma^2 < 0.2$), we proceeded to emulate the AT by generating the attenuation values using a normal distribution with a mean of 10.28 dB and a variance of 0.1 dB, as shown as shown in Fig 4b). The PDF of the generated attenuation can be also seen in Fig 4c).

Using the generated AT, we also measured the SNR of the FSO signal shown in Fig. 4d). The obtained NGMI of both the FSO and mmWave links is shown in Fig. 5a). From the analysis of the NGMI performances, it is noticeable that a slight increase in the attenuation causes a significant dip in the mmWave NGMI. This can be explained by the uneven bitrate division between the two links due to the bandwidth limitations of the mmWave hardware. This becomes more clear from the analysis of Fig. 5b), which shows the evolution of the FSO and mmWave bitrates. When the introduced attenuation increases, the FSO link suffers a reduction of received power and SNR. If the SNR dips below the required for 190 Gbps operation *i.e.* 7.56 dB, the entropy loading algorithm increases the shaping of the FSO signal, thus reducing the bitrate to comply with the NGMI threshold. Conversely, the bitrate of the mmWave link is increased by increasing the entropy of the signal to maintain the total bitrate at 200 Gbps. Thanks to the joint FSO-mmWave entropy loading mechanism, the NGMI performances are kept above a pre-defined threshold of 0.88. A single violation of the NGMI threshold is registered at iteration number 19, where the attenuation suffered by the FSO link requires a complementary bitrate from the mmWave system (> 30 Gbps) that exceeds its capabilities, thus exposing the upper limit of adaptation supported by the proposed hybrid FSO-mmWave system. Finally, Fig. 6 shows the cumulative capacity gain (CCG) defined as $CCG = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{iter}} R_{b_{Total}}(k) - R_{b_{FSO}}(k)$, enabled by the entropy-loaded FSO-mmWave system, w.r.t to the standalone use of the FSO system. After ~ 40 iterations, corresponding to the stronger turbulence impact, a CCG of more than 150 Gbps is demonstrated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed and experimentally demonstrated a hybrid FSO-mmWave transmission system supported by adaptive PCS modulation and cross-domain entropy loading. By using a high-capacity coherent FSO system cooperatively with

Fig. 6: Cumulative capacity gain over each iteration.

a 28 GHz mmWave link, we have demonstrated a reliable 200 Gbps transmission, in which the mmWave link provides up to 30 Gbps compensation to the FSO data-rate reduction imposed turbulence-induced fading, thereby effectively absorbing up to 0.9 dB of SNR variations on the FSO link. Using advanced modulation, these results demonstrate how legacy mmWave technology can be symbiotically merged with next-generation optical wireless systems to enhance their reliability in practical channels suffering from low to mild turbulence. Further gains are expected if novel 6G-oriented RF solutions, such as THz-wave, are similarly combined with FSO.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Alzenad *et al.*, “FSO-Based Vertical Backhaul/Fronthaul Framework for 5G+ Wireless Networks,” *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 218–224, Jan. 2018.
- [2] M. A. Fernandes *et al.*, “Free-Space Terabit Optical Interconnects,” *J. Lightwave Technol.*, pp. 1–1, 2021.
- [3] D. J. Geisler *et al.*, “Atmospheric Emulation and Testing Methodology for Laboratory Verification of FSO Communications Transceivers,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Space Sys. App.*, Oct. 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [4] A. Vavoulas *et al.*, “Weather Effects on FSO Network Connectivity,” *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 4, no. 10, p. 734, Oct. 2012.
- [5] O. Barsimantov *et al.*, “Adaptive Optimization of a Free Space Laser Communication System Under Dynamic Link Attenuation,” *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 3, no. 3, p. 215, Mar. 2011.
- [6] M. Karimi *et al.*, “Novel Adaptive Transmission Algorithms for Free-Space Optical Links,” *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 3808–3815, Dec. 2012.
- [7] M. A. Fernandes *et al.*, “400G MIMO-FSO Transmission with Enhanced Reliability Enabled by Joint LDPC Coding,” in *Proc. Eur. Conf. Opt. Commun.*, Sep. 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [8] F. Buchali *et al.*, “Rate Adaptation and Reach Increase by Probabilistically Shaped 64-QAM: An Experimental Demonstration,” *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 1599–1609, Apr. 2016.
- [9] F. P. Guiomar *et al.*, “Adaptive Probabilistic Shaped Modulation for High-Capacity Free-Space Optical Links,” *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 38, no. 23, pp. 6529–6541, Dec. 2020.
- [10] T. Shi *et al.*, “Hybrid Free Space Optical Communication and Radio Frequency MIMO System for Photonic Interference Separation,” *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 149–152, Feb. 2022.
- [11] M. Giordani *et al.*, “Satellite Communication at Millimeter Waves: A Key Enabler of the 6G Era,” in *2020 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)*. Big Island, HI, USA: IEEE, Feb. 2020, pp. 383–388.
- [12] F. Kschischang *et al.*, “Optimal nonuniform signaling for Gaussian channels,” *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 913–929, May 1993.
- [13] J. Cho *et al.*, “Normalized Generalized Mutual Information as a Forward Error Correction Threshold for Probabilistically Shaped QAM,” in *Proc. Eur. Conf. Opt. Commun.*, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–3.
- [14] J. Bohata *et al.*, “Experimental comparison of DSB and CS-DSB mmW formats over a hybrid fiber and FSO fronthaul network for 5G,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 29, no. 17, p. 27768, Aug. 2021.